

PUBLIC OPINION AND THE CHOICE BETWEEN VIOLENT AND NONVIOLENT CAMPAIGNS

Hiroshi Kenji Takahashi

Department of Political Science, Tokyo Metropolitan University, Tokyo, Japan

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ABSTRACT

The prevalence of nonviolent or violent campaigns varies significantly across countries, raising questions about the factors that shape the strategic choices of civilian collective action. Nonviolent campaigns—such as protests, social movements, and unarmed resistance—have been shown to be more effective in mobilizing public support and achieving government concessions than violent campaigns, which involve the use or threat of physical harm, including armed conflict and violent resistance. While norms favoring nonviolent contestation can constrain campaign behavior, these norms are not universal. In contexts where citizens tolerate or support violence, violent campaigns may gain a mobilization advantage and more effectively achieve political objectives.

This study examines the role of public opinion in determining both the onset and tactical orientation of civil campaigns. By disaggregating public attitudes toward campaign tactics and goals, we explore how societal support—or tolerance—for violence shapes the likelihood of campaigns emerging and the strategies they adopt. Our analysis highlights that public opinion functions as a critical mechanism influencing campaign behavior: widespread support for nonviolent tactics encourages unarmed mobilization, whereas tolerance for violence may incentivize campaigns to adopt coercive or armed strategies. These dynamics provide insight into cross-national variation in campaign methods and the interaction between societal norms and political action.

By linking public sentiment to tactical decisions, this research contributes to understanding why some societies consistently experience nonviolent mobilization while others witness persistent violent conflict. It underscores the importance of considering citizen preferences and societal norms when analyzing the strategic calculus of campaign groups and provides a framework for predicting campaign behavior based on public opinion patterns.

KEYWORDS

Nonviolent Campaigns; Violent Campaigns; Public Opinion; Tactical Choice; Collective Action

Introduction

Why are nonviolent forms of campaigns dominant in some countries while violent forms of campaigns are still relatively frequent in others? We define nonviolent campaigns as civilian collective action using unarmed methods—what previous literature calls social movements, protests, nonviolent resistance, and unarmed struggle—while we define violent campaigns as civilian collective action that uses or threatens physical harm against opposition such as armed conflict, civil war, and violent resistance. Several scholars have examined which is more effective in mobilizing public support and in turn, extracting government concessions, finding that nonviolent campaigns have advantages over violent ones (Franklin, 2009; Chenoweth & Stephan, 2011; Simpson et al., 2018). These findings suggest that norms of nonviolent contestation strongly constrain the behavior of campaign groups and their supporters. However, this does not imply that such norms are universal. If citizens in some countries tolerate violent tactics, then violent campaigns may have a mobilization advantage in winning government concessions when compared to nonviolent campaigns. In this study, we investigate whether public opinion affects the emergence of civil campaigns and their tactical choices, and how these effects are realized by disaggregating public opinion towards campaign tactics and campaign goals.

Using the AmericasBarometer and Afrobarometer surveys, we empirically test the effects of public opinion on civil campaigns, specifically their initiation and tactics. The results show that public satisfaction with the incumbent government, a proxy for public opinion on campaign goals, affects the campaign onset. As the level of democratic satisfaction increases, no campaign is more likely to occur. Additionally, public aversion to violence, a proxy for public opinion about campaign tactics, increases the probability of nonviolent campaigns compared to violent campaigns. The relationships were tested using multinomial logistic regression, as presented in this study, and a probit model with sample selection and logistic regression, as presented in the Appendix. The effect of public opinion remains robust across different model specifications.

This study complements an important strand of research on violent and nonviolent campaigns. Scholars like Stephan and Chenoweth (2008), Chenoweth and Stephan (2011), and Dahl et al. (2020), attribute the supremacy of nonviolent resistance tactics to the public's role as a potential campaign audience based on the results that nonviolent campaigns have mobilization advantages. However, the impact of public opinion has not been rigorously tested, even though it provides significant insights. That is, the findings about the supremacy of nonviolent tactics might be biased toward countries where norms of nonviolence have been established. Furthermore, the radical flank theory, which claims that political groups using peaceful strategies are strengthened by the presence of those using violent strategies (Haines, 1984; Braithwaite, 2013; Wasow, 2020), may also be limited to cases with established nonviolent norms. Although the findings of this study are fairly intuitive, they provide an explicit microfoundation for the relative effectiveness of nonviolent tactics found in relevant literature.

In addition, this study revisits the role of norms in peacefully resolving conflict. Recent studies, like those by Schaftenaar (2017) and Asal et al. (2013), find that higher levels of gender equality increase the probability of nonviolent campaigns. Consistent with these findings, this study also directly reveals that the norms of nonviolence help prevent the occurrence of violent campaigns. This finding provides a significant policy implication that grassroots activities fostering awareness of respectful relationships and peaceful repertoires in conflict resolution are conducive to reducing political violence.

Theoretical considerations

Violent and nonviolent civil campaigns have been predominantly studied as separate phenomena. Violent campaigns have conventionally been examined in the context of civil wars (Cederman et al., 2011; Collier & Hoeffler, 2004; Fearon & Laitin, 2003; Hegre et al., 2001) while nonviolent campaigns have been examined in the context of protests and social movements (Kitschelt, 1986; Tarrow, 2011). Recent studies have focused on a systematic understanding of the choices behind violent and nonviolent tactics. For example, structural factors, such as economically interdependent social networks, influence nonviolent tactics (Butcher & Svensson, 2016), while institutional factors (e.g., regime type) and group attributions (e.g., size, fragmentation, and economic discrimination; existence of other competing campaign groups) influence strategy choices in self-determination disputes (Cunningham, 2013; Cunningham et al., 2017). International factors, like globalization, are thought to influence the emergence of nonviolent campaigns (Karakaya, 2018). While this line of inquiry is conducive to understanding the patterns of campaign tactics used by dissidents, it does not explicitly examine the impact of non-participatory citizens, whose importance is argued by several qualitative studies (DeNardo, 1985; McCarthy & Zald, 1977; Schumaker, 1975).

It should be noted that while some research emphasizes sequencing in tactics (Regan & Norton, 2005), this study focuses on the impact of non-participatory citizens on campaign groups' initial strategic choices. Admittedly, some campaign groups might substitute nonviolent tactics for violent tactics once they find the latter to be unsuccessful or vice versa. However, Dahl et al. (2020) state that whether they substitute one type of tactic for the other is "a second-order issue compared to accounting for initial tactic choice" (p. 6) and that substitution does not frequently occur.

Following this assertion, we defer an examination of tactical substitution to future research.

Citizens who do not participate in campaigns significantly affect the course of civil campaigns, constraining the behavior of both governments and campaign groups. In democracies and electoral authoritarian states, although to a lesser extent, citizens have de jure power to select and punish political leaders in elections and hence affect their political decisions (Fearon, 1999; Smith, 1998); they can affect the de facto power of campaign groups by supporting or opposing their activities (Burstein, 2003). Even in autocracies, as exemplified by Color Revolutions in postcommunist states, and the Arab Spring, citizens can have considerable influence over regime survival (Teorell, 2010; Tucker, 2007). Thus, to make campaigns successful, campaign groups must consider not only the reactions of government but also public opinion. Citizens observe campaign leaders' claims, compare preferences between existing policies and their alternatives, estimate the likelihood of campaign success and government repression, and determine whether to support the campaign.

Simpson et al. (2018) and Huff and Kruszewska (2016) explore the relationship between tactical choices and public opinion. They find that use of violence by a campaign group reduces identification with the group and, in turn, reduces public support for the violent group. Similarly, Lupu and Wallace (2019) find that violent tactics raise public support for government repression while Thomas and Louis (2014) show that nonviolent collective actions can more effectively communicate the illegitimacy of the status quo to the public. Likewise, scholars such as Haines (1984), Anner (2009), Braithwaite (2013, and Wasow (2020) argue that citizens are more likely to support moderates than radicals. These studies argue that nonviolent campaigns have an advantage over violent campaigns in mobilizing public endorsements, while taking for granted that people conform to norms of nonviolent contestation. Nonetheless, such norms are not necessarily universal, as illustrated in Figure 1. This suggests that violent campaign groups may successfully mobilize supporters in societies where the norms of

nonviolent contestation are weak. In such cases, the occurrence of violent campaigns is more probable than in societies where more people internalize moral conscience, as in established democracies.

We argue that public opinion is expected to affect the course of campaigns in two ways. First, the public considers campaign goals when deciding whether to support campaigns. If campaign goals focus on the interests of a wide population, campaign leaders can increase their participation and receive sufficient financial aid, making it difficult for the government to ignore the campaign. Conversely, campaign leaders may abandon campaign plans due to lack of resources, if they feel that most citizens are satisfied with the government, or if their campaign interests only cater to a small audience. Hence, public opinion on campaign goals substantially affects decisions to initiate campaigns. Consistently, Dahl et al. (2020) argue that the potential size of the support base (e.g., secessionist or governmental conflict) affects campaign groups' initial tactical choices given the campaign onset, but they do not examine how it affects campaign groups' initial decisions on whether to challenge.

Second, the public cares about campaign tactics. Some campaign groups use weapons, resulting in the deaths of civilians and soldiers while others make demands through nonviolent campaigns, using peaceful protests and sit-ins. The form of campaign tactics matters for the public since violent and nonviolent forms of campaigns require different types of resources and levels of risk (Cunningham, 2013, p. 294). Peaceful campaigns often involve low levels of physical damage and repression, while violent campaigns can lead to numerous injuries and deaths. This is supported by Lupu and Wallace's (2019) empirical analyses, which show violent campaigns consistently increase popular support for government repression against them. Depending on the strength of the public's norms of nonviolent contestation, campaign groups might strategically switch their plans regarding campaign form from nonviolence to violence or vice versa.

Furthermore, the extent to which the public is averse to violence constrains government reactions to violent and nonviolent campaigns. When public's aversion to violence is high, the public tends to criticize the government for yielding to violent campaigns. For instance, political leaders often pledge never to speak with terrorists to avoid legitimizing their radical means (Toros, 2008). In contrast, a government risks denouncements by rejecting citizens' peaceful demands. Such a backlash against state repression is conceivably less likely when armed groups are repressed (Martin, 2007; Sharp & Paulson, 2005). Thus, campaign leaders are expected to choose nonviolent tactics, especially in situations of high public intolerance of violence, to facilitate government concessions for nonviolent campaigns. Conversely, campaign leaders may use violent tactics when citizens prioritize the achievement of campaign goals over the norms of nonviolent contestation, as compromising with violent campaigns and rejecting nonviolent campaigners' demands should be less costly for governments.

The Orange Revolution in Ukraine illustrates this. Learning from a previous lapse into violent clashes, leaders were careful to inhibit aggression in their massive support. They used less aggressive protests during the presidential campaign—meetings, concerts, and marches (Shukan, 2011). Furthermore, to avoid clashes between Yushchenko and Yanukovich supporters; protesters and police, human buffer zones were created between rival camps, police, and crowds, and trained volunteers patrolled the area (Binnendijk & Marovic, 2006). Law enforcement interviewed by Binnendijk and Marovic (2006) reported that the Yushchenko camp made every effort to avert conflict. The campaign group's persistent use of nonviolent tactics exemplifies public aversion to violence. Consistently, a 2004 public opinion survey revealed that almost two-thirds of respondents saw negotiations among elites as an acceptable means to resolve a crisis, with only 19% opposition (Kudelia, 2010, p. 182).

Figure 1 shows varying levels of public approval in the use of violence in different countries. Several respondents prefer nonviolent approaches to violent ones, which is consistent with the fact that individuals and groups rarely resort to violence (Chenoweth & Stephan, 2011, p. 32). For example, a 2011 survey in Uruguay found that 84.1% of the participants strongly disapproved of violence. Figure 1 also shows that not all countries are intolerant to the use of political violence. Some countries show relatively high public approval for violent forms of dissidence. In 2007, only 33.9% of the people in Panama showed a strong preference for nonviolent approaches. This seems to be consistent with the rare and unignorable history of violent campaigns, such as those in Sri Lanka, Pakistan, East Timor, and El Salvador. There is more than a 0.5 difference between the maximum and minimum values of violence aversion. The leader of a country in which more than 80% of the public disapproves of the use of violence could face different ramifications to accommodate the demands posed by violent campaigns compared to the leader of a country in which only 30% of the population is intolerant of violence. If a government accepts the demands posed by violent campaigns in the latter case, it is expected that more people will disapprove of the demands and criticize the government. Figure 1 clearly shows that the preference for nonviolence is not uniform and is contrary to the literature that supports its supremacy. Moreover, countries differ substantially in the degree to which violence is perceived as a legitimate tactic. This variance can be the result of civil wars, military coups, and peaceful resistance experienced by individual nations.

Figure 1.

Histogram for the public's violence aversion in Latin America and Africa

Note. The AmericasBarometer asked the respondents about the degree to which they tolerated the use of violent means for political purposes in 2008, 2010, 2012, and 2014. The Afrobarometer asked respondents whether violence is justified or not in Rounds 2, 3, and 5. Violence aversion corresponds to the proportion of respondents who are relatively intolerant to the use of violence. Regarding the details of the measurement of violence aversion, please see Section 4, where we provide detailed explanations of this variable.

Based on these arguments, we propose the following three hypotheses concerning the impact of public opinion on campaign leaders' initial tactical choices:

Hypothesis 1a. Higher levels of public satisfaction with the democratic process of a country predict a lower probability of the emergence of a nonviolent campaign, when compared to no campaigns.

Hypothesis 1b. Higher levels of public satisfaction with the democratic process of a country predict a lower probability of the emergence of a violent campaign, when compared to no campaigns.

Hypothesis 2. Higher levels of public aversion to violence predict a higher probability for the emergence of a nonviolent campaign, when compared to a violent campaign.

In the following sections, we confirm that the public's evaluation of an incumbent government and their attitudes toward violent methods constrain the choice of campaign tactics.

Research Design

This section examines the empirical support for the three hypotheses above. This study used survey questions from the AmericasBarometer and Afrobarometer to evaluate public attitudes toward the political violence. These barometers contain individual-level information on opinions regarding the use of political violence for 27 Latin American and 34 African countries, conducted over several years. We aggregated individual-level information at the country–year level, and thus, our unit of analysis was country–year. Because surveys with opinion questions are not conducted every year, the year in our sample is unbalanced. Due to missing values for the variables used below, some countries were excluded from the sample.

There are 156 observations for analysis from 49 countries. The countries in our sample are Colombia, Venezuela, Guyana, Ecuador, Peru, Brazil, Bolivia, Paraguay, Chile, Argentina, Uruguay, Haiti, Dominican Republic, Mali, Senegal, Benin, Burkina Faso, Liberia, Sierra Leone,

Ghana, Togo, Cameroon, Nigeria, Uganda, Kenya, Jamaica, Tanzania, Burundi, Mozambique, Zambia, Zimbabwe, Malawi, South Africa, Namibia, Lesotho, Botswana, Madagascar, Mauritius, Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Egypt, Mexico, Guatemala, Honduras, El Salvador, Nicaragua, Costa Rica, and Panama. We excluded the United States and Canada since, in these countries, violent campaigns in our definition are extremely rare, and norms of violence aversion have constantly maintained high values, lacking variation. Some studies use AmericasBarometer while only focusing on Latin American countries (Machado et al., 2011).

Explanatory variables

Violence aversion

As the degree of public intolerance toward use of violence for political aims was one of the main explanatory variables, we employed the following survey questions. As presented in Appendix Table A, the AmericasBarometer asked, “Please tell me how strongly you would approve or disapprove of people participating in a group working to violently overthrow an elected government.” The answers provided were as follows: 1 = strongly disapprove; 2–9; 10 = strongly approve; I don't know; no response; not applicable; and not asked in this country or year. This question was asked in four rounds (2008, 2010, 2012, and 2014) in the AmericasBarometer survey by the Latin American Public Opinion Project (LAPOP), which is available at www.LapopSurveys.org. The precise wording of the questions differs slightly by survey year, but the point remains the same. The 2006 questionnaire asked, ‘How strongly would you approve or disapprove [of] people [participating] in a group wanting to carry out a violent overthrow of an elected government?’ The 2004 questionnaire asked, “How firmly would you approve or disapprove [of] people [participating] in a group wanting to remove an elected government by violent means?”

From the Afrobarometer, we used the following question: “Which of the following statements is closest to your view? Choose Statements 1 or 2. Statement 1: The use of violence is never justified in [the country's] politics

today. Statement 2: In this country, it is sometimes necessary to use violence in support of a just cause.” The answers were as follows: 1 = agree very strongly with statement 1; 2 = agree with statement 1; 3 = agree with statement 2; 4 = agree very strongly with statement 2; 5 = agree with neither; 6 = don’t know; 7 = refuse to answer. This question was asked in Rounds 2, 3, and 5 in the Afrobarometer. While the questions are not worded similarly in the Afrobarometer and AmericasBarometer, we find these questions comparable and suitable for measuring public preference for violent campaign tactics. Each investigates respondent general attitudes toward the political violence, rather than their attitudes toward the use of violence by particular groups (e.g., police violence), or in broader contexts (e.g., intra-family violence, violence against others). Latin American and African countries have witnessed government turnovers through military coups and riots, and some countries, such as Colombia, have experienced violent conflicts until recently. Latin America experienced 72 successful coups between 1950 and 2015 (Powell & Thyne, 2011). Africa experienced 88 successful coups between 1952 and 2012 (Souaré, 2014). Regarding riots, for example, the Indigenous movement largely contributed to democratization in Ecuador by joining a group of military officers (Zamosc, 2007, p. 2). One might suspect the comparability between these two questions. If a factor differentiating these two questions also influences the outcome, the observed relationship between the *violence aversion* variable and dependent variable is spurious. To account for the omitted variable, we control for a dummy variable, *Africa*, which takes the value of 1 if the country is in the African region; otherwise, it takes 0. We further tackle this problem by splitting the samples and discussing the results and their interpretation in the Appendix. This study used merged samples in the main analysis since, as explained in the Appendix, splitting the sample yielded too few observations to implement the full model.

The variable, *violence aversion*, reflects the percentage of respondents who chose strongly disapprove, 2, 3, 4, or 5 in the case of the AmericasBarometer, and 1 or 2 in the case of the Afrobarometer. As one might suspect discrepancies between the answers to the different questions asked in the respective surveys, in estimating a model, we control for continent. To check whether extremists’ opinions mattered, we used *violence aversion 2*, which reflects the percentage of respondents who chose strongly disapprove or 2 in the AmericasBarometer and 1 in the Afrobarometer. The former measurement captured respondents who were relatively intolerant of violence, while the latter measurement captured respondents who were extremely intolerant of the use of political violence. A model with the latter measurement (*violence aversion 2*) can be found in the Appendix Tables C and D. Therefore, a higher value for *violence aversion* reflects a higher level of public intolerance of the use of violence for political purposes. We used a one-year lag for this indicator to account for reverse causality problems.

Satisfaction with democracy

Public opinion about campaign goals is theoretically an important factor affecting civil campaigns but is rarely considered a variable for cross-national statistical analyses due to the lack of worldwide data measuring people’s attitudes towards the goals of individual campaign groups. To measure public opinion on the goals of campaign groups at the country level, we used survey questions evaluating the level of public satisfaction with the incumbent government.

We operationalize it in this way for three reasons. First, government performance is expected to affect the potential size of campaign supporters. If many people are frustrated with the government’s poor performance, alternative policies proposed by campaign groups have a higher chance of mobilizing supporters. In contrast, if public satisfaction with the incumbent government is high, the campaign groups’ goals are considered less

favorable. Dahl et al. (2020) also argue that the goals of campaign groups (e.g., secession for a minority or the removal of unpopular government) are closely related to their potential for mobilization. Second, it is difficult to survey public opinion on the goals of individual campaign groups. Large numbers of civil groups exist within individual countries, with some operating only in restricted regions, challenging assumptions that citizens would have formed opinions about each group. Third, were we able to access public opinion data on the goals of individual campaign groups, aggregating group-level data into cross-national data might offset the level of public support for each campaign goal given diversity of political preferences. While this is not a straightforward operationalization, public satisfaction with the incumbent government can be a proxy for public opinion on campaign goals.

Specifically, we used survey questions regarding public satisfaction with the existing government in AmericasBarometer and Afrobarometer. The AmericasBarometer asked, “In general, would you say that you are very satisfied, satisfied, dissatisfied, or very dissatisfied with the way democracy works in [name of participant’s country]?” The answers provided were very satisfied; satisfied; dissatisfied; very dissatisfied; I don’t know; no response; and not applicable. The Afrobarometer asked, “Overall, how satisfied are you with the way democracy works in the country?” Responses were given as follows: 0 = the country is not a democracy; 1 = not at all satisfied; 2 = not very satisfied; 3 = fairly satisfied; 4 = very satisfied; 9 = don’t know; 998 = refused to answer; and -1 = missing. *Satisfaction with democracy* measured the proportion of respondents who chose the answers very satisfied and satisfied for the AmericasBarometer, and 3 and 4 in the Afrobarometer. This implies that a higher value corresponds to a higher level of public satisfaction with the democratic governance of that country. We use a one-year lag for this indicator to account for reverse causality problems.

Dependent variables

We operationalized *violent campaigns* using two datasets to investigate how the level of public intolerance of violence affects the occurrence of violent resistance. *Violent campaigns* variable marks the onset of armed conflict, as defined by the Georeferenced Event Dataset (GED) version 18.1 (2017) of the Uppsala Conflict Data Program ([UCDP]; Sundberg & Melander 2013), the Armed Conflict Dataset version 18.1 of the UCDP/Peace Research Institute Oslo ([PRIO];

Allansson et al., 2017, Gleditsch et al., 2002), and the Mass Mobilization Data Project (MMD; Clark & Regan, 2016). This study does not use the NAVCO dataset (Chenoweth & Lewis 2013; Chenoweth et al., 2018; Chenoweth & Shay, 2022) because the NAVCO dataset only covers largescale, highly salient protests and ignores others that the MMD covers. For instance, in the case of Mozambique, the MMD reports the presence of protest in 1990-1998;2000-2001; 2003-2005; and 2008-2016. However, in NAVCO1.3, only the Front for the Liberation of Mozambique 1962-1975, and Renamo 1979-1992, are reported. Furthermore, several international news outlets such as BBC (2010), Reuters (Mangwiro, 2010), and Guardian (Patel, 2010) reported the occurrence of largescale food riots in Mozambique in 2010, but this campaign was overlooked in the NAVCO. The *violent campaigns* variable has a value of 1, if there is at least one violent event initiated by a nonstate group in a given year. Importantly, even if there is only one violent event, we consider it a violent campaign. Previous literature has overlooked the implications of one violent event in considering the tactical choices of campaign groups by classifying the types of campaign groups according to their dominant form of tactics. However, even if there is only one violent event, campaign leaders always face a choice to engage in violence for the campaign. In this sense, the campaign group should consider both the consequences of violence and the degree of violence accepted by the public. Thus, our theory applies to campaigns followed by a sequence of events and those represented by

one event. Therefore, even if there was only one violent event, we used a value of 1 for the *violent campaigns* variable.

Second, we used a *nonviolent campaigns* variable, which has a value of 1, if a country has experienced at least one nonviolent campaign, as defined by the Mass Mobilization Data Project (Clark & Regan, 2016), without experiencing violent campaigns in a given year. The Mass Mobilization Data Project covers any protest event between 1990 and 2014 that targeted the government and mobilized at least 50 people. It also records whether the protest event involved violence against the state, such as destroying property or shooting at the police or the military. Therefore, we consider that a country experienced a nonviolent campaign if at least one peaceful protest was conducted in the country during a given year, without experiencing violent campaigns defined in the previous paragraph.

Finally, to make the comparison between no campaigns and campaigns, we used the *no campaign* variable, which takes a value of 1, if a country experienced neither violent nor nonviolent campaigns in a given year. Using these three dummy variables, we created a categorical dependent variable that takes three values: *violent campaigns*; *nonviolent campaigns*; and *no campaigns*. When both violent and nonviolent campaigns were observed, we classified such observations as *violent campaigns*. Therefore, violent campaign here means that the country in a given year observed at least one violent event while nonviolent campaign means that the country in a given year only experienced nonviolent campaigning. As a robustness check, instead of using the categorical dependent variable, we used a binary measurement of violent campaign where the sample included countries experiencing any types of campaigns. Out of 156 observations, 80 observations were coded as *violent campaigns*, 38 observations were coded as *nonviolent campaigns*, and 38 observations were coded as *no campaigns*.

Control variables

As might be expected, public attitude toward the use of violence can be affected by previous violent incidents in that country. If citizens are accustomed to violence, they may become tolerant to further instances of violence. Violent incidents in the past can predict the recurrence of violent campaigns, and a country might experience a vicious cycle of violent campaigns led by rebel groups. Therefore, considering the endogeneity problem, we control for past violent campaigns ($t-1$'s logged number of violent events).

Preference for democracy

Pursuing political goals by using force is incongruent with democratic principles that place the utmost value on peaceful ways of resolving conflict, including elections, deliberations, and negotiations. Thus, democratic support should also positively indicate an intolerance for violence. We controlled for the *preference for democracy* variable as excluding the preference for regime types would result in underestimating the effect of public opinion on violence. For this variable, in the case of the AmericasBarometer, we used the question, "Which of the following statements do you agree with most?" Responses were given as follows: 1 = for people like me, it doesn't matter whether a government is democratic or non-democratic; 2 = democracy is preferable to any other form of government; 3 = under some circumstances, an authoritarian government may be preferable to a democratic one; a = I don't know; b = no response; c = not applicable; and z = not asked in this country or year. In the case of the Afrobarometer, we used the following question: "Which of these three statements is closest to your own opinion?" Responses were given as follows: 1 = democracy is preferable to any other kind of government; 2 = in some circumstances, a non-democratic government can be preferable; and 3 = for someone like me, it doesn't matter what kind of government we have. As a value for *preference for democracy*, we

calculated the proportion of respondents that chose 2 in the AmericasBarometer and 1 in the Afrobarometer. A higher value of this variable implies a higher level of public support for democracy.

GDP per capita/population

We controlled for GDP per capita as a proxy for state capacity. Fearon and Laitin (2003) argue that weak governments make insurgency more feasible by presenting a statistically significant negative relationship between GDP per capita and the onset of civil war. Furthermore, the population has a considerable influence on rebellions. Fearon (2004) asserts that populous countries enable the mobility of insurgent groups. Moreover, Chenoweth and Lewis (2013) demonstrated that large populations are positively associated with the onset of both violent and nonviolent resistance. We use the log transformation for GDP per capita and population as the distribution of these variables is positively skewed.

Polity2

Autocratic regimes frequently use repression in politics through military, police, and security agencies (Svolik, 2012), influencing public perceptions of the political violence. For example, repression is still conducted in many anocracies in Africa. In addition, Hegre et al. (2001) found that civil wars are more likely to happen in intermediate regimes. Moreover, Machado et al. (2011) demonstrated that weaker political institutions are associated with the frequent use of nonelectoral means for expressing preferences. If campaign groups can express their preferences via democratic means such as elections, and if their preferences are reflected in policies, then they could use means other than launching nonviolent or violent campaigns. Weaker political institutions could also influence public attitudes toward the use of political violence, thus justifying the use of violence among the citizens. Therefore, we control for *polity2* from the Polity IV Data Project (Marshall et al., 2018). We included a linear term for this variable, where the maximum value of 10 indicates the most developed democracy, while the minimum value of -10 indicates the most developed autocracy.

Political Terror Scale (PTS)

Regan and Norton (2005) found that higher levels of repression lead to fewer civil wars and more protests. In relation to our main explanatory variable, *violence aversion*, we suspected that growing levels of repression may fuel public approval of political violence. To reduce the resulting potential for omitted variable bias, we controlled for government repression. Following the study by Regan and Norton (2005), we used the Political Terror Scale (Gibney & Dalton, 1996; Wood & Gibney, 2010). We relied on state department data, which uses discrete numbers from 1 to 5. Here, higher values indicate higher levels of repression.

Mortality rate, infant, female

Schaftenaar (2017) finds that increases in gender equality increase the likelihood of nonviolent conflict onset. As gender norms may affect the strategic choices used by campaign groups, we controlled for fertility rate (total births per woman), from the World Bank dataset, as an indicator of gender equality (Caprioli, 2005; Schaftenaar, 2017). As a robustness check, we also used *primary completion rate, female (percentage of relevant age group)* as an alternative measurement for gender equality (Appendix Tables L and M).

All control variables were lagged for one year to account for the endogeneity problem.

Ethnic fractionalisation

Schneider and Wiesehomeier (2008) and Taydas and Peksen (2012) found that ethnic fractionalization is positively associated with the onset of civil war. We also suspect that higher ethnic fractionalization is positively associated with the onset of all types of campaigns due to grievances across different ethnic groups. Therefore, ethnic fractionalization was included as a control variable. Information on ethnic fractionalization was taken

from Fearon and Laitin (2003). As the data cover only until 1999, we use the information on 1999 as our information on static ethnic fractionalization. Table 1 presents descriptive statistics for all variables explained so far.

Table 1

Descriptive statistics

				Min	Max
N		Mean	St. Dev		
Violent campaigns	156	0.513	0.501	0	1
Campaigns	156	0.756	0.431	0	1
Violence aversion	156	0.862	0.075	0.572	1
Violence aversion 2	156	0.614	0.155	0.235	0.901
Satisfaction for democracy	156	0.544	0.146	0.200	0.894
GDP per capita (ln)	156	12.580	1.717	9.357	17.020
Population (ln)	156	16.336	1.283	13522	19.135
Preference for democracy	156	0.847	0.071	0.568	1
Polity2	156	6.455	3.372	-4	10
PTS	156	2.872	0.833	1	5
Ethnic fractionalization	156	0.413	0.301	0.014	0.925
Fertility rate	156	3.359	1.386	1.44	6.842
Africa	156	0.391	0.490	0	1
Violent campaigns count (ln)	156	1.026	1.326	0.000	5.617
Campaigns count (ln)	156	1.529	1.266	0.000	5.620

Empirical Findings

We employed multinomial logistic regression to compare the probabilities of each outcome: violent campaigns, nonviolent campaigns, or no campaigns. To assess the Independence of Irrelevant Alternatives (IIA) assumption, we conducted a Hausman test. The test result showed that the IIA has not been violated. Table 2 presents the results obtained from the multinomial logit model, where we use nonviolent campaign as the base. Table 3 presents the results of the multinomial logit model, where we use no campaigns as the base.

Regarding the effect of public satisfaction levels with democracy, Table 2 shows a positive and statistically significant relationship between *satisfaction with democracy* and *no campaigns*, when compared to *nonviolent campaigns*. Figure 2 shows how the predicted probability of the outcome *no campaigns*, compared to the outcome of *nonviolent campaigns*, changes depending on different values of *satisfaction with democracy* while holding values of other variables at their mean values. The figure shows that as the public becomes more satisfied with democracy, *no campaigns* are more likely to occur, when compared to *nonviolent campaigns*. When the value of *satisfaction with democracy* is 0, the predicted probability of no campaigns relative to nonviolent campaigns is 0.005 while that of predicted probability, when the value of the variable is 1, is 0.730. There is 0.725 percentage point increase. Moreover, Table 3 shows that there is a negative and statistically

Table 2

Multinomial logistic regression

	No campaigns	Violent campaigns
Violence aversion	-3.090(3.990)	-7.942** (3.984)
Preference for democracy	-3.820(4.833)	1.362(3.931)
Satisfaction for democracy	5.752*** (2.184)	-0.774(2.000)
GDP per capita (ln)	0.815* (0.492)	0.684(0.429)
Population (ln)	-1.436*** (0.525)	-0.591(0.535)
Polity2	-0.015(0.078)	0.141*(0.076)
PTS	0.677* (0.386)	0.519(0.364)
Ethnic fractionalisation	-4.095** (1.737)	-1.340(0.907)
Fertility rate	1.102* (0.567)	0.601(0.395)
Africa	0.384(0.780)	0.612(0.668)
Violent campaigns count (ln)	-0.394(0.524)	0.906** (0.395)
Intercept	11.820** (5.998)	3.145(6.032)
Observations	156	
Log pseudo likelihood	-119.561	
AIC	287.123	

Note. GDP=gross domestic product; PTS=Political Terror Scale; AIC=Akaike information criterion; standard errors are clustered by country; * p < 0.1; ** p < 0.05; *** p < 0.01. Base line is *nonviolent campaigns*.

Figure 2

Predicted probability of no campaign compared to nonviolent campaign

Note: X-axis shows different values of satisfaction for democracy. The dotted lines are 95% confidence intervals.

Table 3
Multinomial logistic regression

	Violent campaigns
Violence aversion	-4.852(2.950)
Preference for democracy	5.181(4.328)
Satisfaction for democracy	-6.526** (2.877)
GDP per capita (ln)	-0.131(0.460)
Population (ln)	0.845(0.568)
Polity2	0.156(0.114)
PTS	-0.158(0.404)
Ethnic fractionalisation	2.755(1.899)
Fertility rate	-0.500(0.526)
Africa	0.227(0.879)
Violent campaigns count (ln)	1.300*** (0.380)
Intercept	-8.675(5.521)
Observations	156
Log pseudo likelihood	-119.561
AIC	287.123

Note. GDP=gross domestic product; PTS=Political Terror Scale; AIC=Akaike information criterion; standard errors are clustered by country; * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$. Baseline is *no campaigns*.

Significant relationship between *satisfaction with democracy* and *violent campaigns*, when compared to *no campaigns*. Figure 3 shows how the predicted probability of the outcome *violent campaigns* compared to the outcome *no campaign*, changes depending on different values of *satisfaction with democracy* while holding values of other variables at their mean values. The figure shows that as the public becomes more satisfied with democracy, *violent campaigns* are less likely to occur, when compared to *no campaigns*. When the value of *satisfaction with democracy* is 0, the predicted probability of violent campaigns relative to no campaigns is 0.805 while that of predicted probability, when the value of the variable is 1, is 0.179. There is 0.626 percentage point decrease. These findings support Hypotheses 1a and 1b, aligned with the implication of Machado et al.’s (2011) finding that weaker political institutions are associated with more frequent use of alternative means for expressing preferences. Our findings suggest that citizens’ perceptions about the performance of political institutions are important, and are more than an objective evaluation

Figure 3

Predicted probability of violent campaign compared to no campaign

than an objective evaluation of institutions (i.e. *polity2*). When the public is satisfied with democratic functions, they feel their preferences have been addressed within the conventional political arena. Consequently, campaign groups are less likely to gain support, which results in fewer campaigns, when compared to both non-violent and violent campaigns. It is noteworthy that public opinion about campaign tactics (i.e. *violence aversion*) does not have a significant effect on the campaign onset, meaning (1) the comparison between the *no campaigns* and *nonviolent campaigns* in Table 2, and (2) the comparison between *no campaigns* and *violent campaigns* in Table 3. Consistent with our argument, this suggests that campaign leaders would devote more attention to the size of their potential sympathizers when deciding whether to launch campaigns, rather than considering which campaign tactics will be more effective, given the public opinion on violence.

The emergence of civil campaigns is exemplified in contemporary Chile. Following student protests against increasing subway fares in October 2019, thousands of people started campaigns for the improvement of socioeconomic issues like poverty, income distribution, and education (Bonney and Krauss, 2019). However, according to statistics from the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, the average wage income, the ratio of elderly in poverty, and the Gini index have steadily improved since the 2000s (Kitano, 2020, pp. 20–23). Kitano (2020) claimed that the rashness of public frustrations, despite such substantial improvements, was associated with the country’s accession to the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) in 2010. While the media had positively reported Chile’s socioeconomic performance by comparing it to that of other Latin American countries before this accession, Chilean people made extremely negative assessments, when compared to other OECD countries (Kitano, 2020, pp. 23–25). This change in Chilean people’s perceptions about their government’s performance led to the outbreak of civil campaigns.

Regarding the effect of aversion toward violence on the likelihood of *violent campaigns*, Table 2 shows that there is a negative and statistically significant relationship between *violence aversion* and *violent campaigns*, when compared to *nonviolent campaigns*. Figure 4 shows how the predicted probability of *violent campaigns* compared to *nonviolent campaigns* changes depending on different values of *violence aversion* while holding the values of other variables at their mean values. When the value of *violence aversion* is 0, the predicted probability of *violent campaigns* relative to *nonviolent campaigns* is 0.996 while that of predicted probability, when the value of the variable is 1, is 0.403. There is 0.593 percentage point decrease. As the public becomes more intolerant toward

political violence, *violent campaigns* are less likely to happen, when compared to *nonviolent campaigns*. This implies that the public’s intolerance of violence leads to a lower likelihood of *violent campaigns*, especially when campaigns are launched, supporting Hypothesis 2. We should note that the effect of *violence aversion* remains strong after controlling for regime type, GDP per capita, and ethnic fractionalization.

Although the sample size (156) might not have been large enough to implement the selection model, in Appendix Table B, we employed a probit model with sample selection. In this version, we estimated two stages of probabilities: (1) the likelihood of all types of campaigns, and (2) the likelihood of violent campaigns given the campaign onset. The results obtained from this sample selection model were similar to those obtained from the multinomial logistic regression.

Figure 4

Predicted probability of violent campaign compared to nonviolent campaign

This model shows that an increase in *satisfaction with democracy* is negatively associated with the likelihood of any type of campaign. Moreover, this model shows that as the public becomes less tolerant of the political violence, *violent campaigns* are less likely to occur than *nonviolent campaigns*. Further, in the Appendix Table G, we also estimated a model where we used samples that observed any types of campaigns and used a dummy variable of *violent campaigns* as the dependent variable, comparing *nonviolent campaigns* only versus *violent campaigns*. The result shows that public intolerance of violence is negatively related to *violent campaigns*. As another robustness check, we also estimated models without control variables in the Appendix Tables E and F, keeping two main independent variables: *satisfaction with democracy* and *violence aversion*. The relationship of the main independent variables, observed in the full model of the main text, was robust in the parsimonious model.

Interestingly, the robustness check results using the *violence aversion 2* variable in the Appendix Tables C and D show that the relationship between *violence aversion 2* and *violent campaigns* compared to *nonviolent campaigns* is not statistically significant. As mentioned, *violence aversion 2* evaluates how results change if we use the proportion of opinions that explicitly oppose the use of political violence, instead of using the proportion of those who disagree with the use of political violence. The robustness check implies that opinions that are closer to the median opinion matter, rather than the opinion of a small group of extremists.

Findings thus far complement an important strand of research on violent and nonviolent campaigns. Recent studies from Stephan and Chenoweth (2008), Chenoweth and Stephan (2011), and Dahl et al. (2020), attribute the supremacy of nonviolent campaign tactics to the mobilization advantage of nonviolent campaigns and based on this empirical result, infer that the public as a potential campaign audience matters during civil resistance campaigns. While previous studies did not directly test the relationship between public opinion and the course of resistance regardless of the assumption, we directly exploit public opinion data and demonstrate that the findings of previous literature can hold only where the moral force of nonviolence is already strong. In other words, where the use of violence is still deemed justifiable, nonviolent campaigns might not necessarily be more effective than violent ones in mobilizing participants and extracting government concessions. The findings of this study provide an explicit microfoundation for the relative effectiveness of nonviolent tactics found in the relevant literature. Moreover, importantly, compared to previous studies showing the relationship between gender norms and campaign tactics (Asal et al., 2013; Schaftenaar, 2017), our study shows that nonviolent norms beyond gender also matter to campaign tactics. Nonviolent norms at the country level, which assert that the use of political violence is not justifiable, significantly influence campaign tactics deployed.

Regarding the implications for the control variables, as is expected, when the number of past violent events increases, the likelihood of current violent campaigns increases compared to both nonviolent campaigns and no campaigns (positively significant at a 95% interval level in Table 2 and 99% interval level in Table 3). In terms of other control variables, ethnic fractionalization provides an interesting finding. Previous studies found no relationship between ethnic fractionalization and civil war (Fearon & Laitin, 2003). As indicated in Table 2, ethnic fractionalization is negatively related to the onset of no campaign relative to nonviolent campaigns (significant at a 95% interval level). Our findings imply that although ethnic fractionalization does not influence the method of campaigning, it could influence the decision to mobilize in the first place, especially nonviolent campaigns. This is in alignment with the classical theory that grievances serve as a significant mobilization mechanism (Gurr, 1970). Finally, in populous countries, *no campaigns* is less likely to occur compared to *nonviolent campaigns* (significant at a 99% interval level, Table 2). This may be related to potential mobilization capacity: Having more potential audiences that can be mobilized provides a comparative advantage regarding nonviolent tactics (Dahl et al., 2020).

Conclusion

This study explores how public opinion concerning campaign goals and tactics affects campaign leaders' behavior. Our empirical analyses using the AmericasBarometer and Afrobarometer provide evidence. Empirical results support the hypothesis that as the levels of public satisfaction with the democratic process of a country increases, nonviolent campaigns and violent ones respectively become less likely, when compared to no campaigns. This means that satisfaction with democracy decreases the onset of nonviolent and violent campaigns. Finally, the empirical results support the hypothesis that as the level of public aversion to violence increases, the predicted probability of the emergence of a nonviolent campaign increases when compared to a violent campaign. These findings contribute to understanding the radical flank effect. The radical flank effect refers to the positive effect of political groups with radical ideology and tactics have on those with moderate ideology and tactics. Our findings suggest that such supremacy of nonviolent campaigns presented in the literature on radical flank theory might also be limited to cases with established norms of nonviolent contestation.

This study yields several avenues for future research. First, future research should analyze the dynamic mechanisms of how norms of nonviolence will change according to the onset of violent and nonviolent

campaigns and how that change will shape patterns of new campaigns. Second, future research could investigate ideological factors other than attitudes towards violence like gender attitudes. Indeed, Dahlum and Wig (2020) find that one of the mechanisms by which female political empowerment leads to civil peace is a female-friendly culture. As Forsberg and Olsson (2021) point out the importance of scrutinizing different types of gender norms, how gender norms affect attitudes toward violence and gender attitudes themselves constrain mobilization would be important to further unpack campaign tactics, ultimately conflict resolution— transformation from violence to nonviolence. Finally, given that this study used a dummy measurement in operationalizing the dependent variable, it would also be important to investigate beyond the binary measurement. It is important to theorize and test how public opinion influences the relative size of campaigns or how it influences the tactical change of campaigns. Considering that size has been identified as an important factor for campaigns outcome (Chenoweth & Stephan, 2011; Dahl et al., 2020; Franklin, 2009; Stephan & Chenoweth, 2008), identifying how public opinion could influence campaign size would be beneficial for understanding campaign success. For better or worse, public opinion is influenced by various interventions or programs such as education, development of civil society, or media. Pursuing these avenues would ultimately enrich our understanding of how peaceful resolution of conflict could be possible without resorting to violence.

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